

RADIOLOGICAL AND FUNCTIONAL OUTCOMES OF CLOSED REDUCTION AND ARTHROGRAPHY FOLLOWED BY HIP SPICA IN DEVELOPMENTAL DYSPLASIA OF THE HIP IN CHILDREN UNDER 18 MONTHS

Zain Ullah^{*1}, Ismail Khan², Mehtab Ullah³

^{1,2}Consultant Orthopedic Surgeon, Type D Hospital Jamrud, Khyber, Peshawar

³Specialist Orthopedic Surgery, Type D Hospital Jamrud, Khyber, Peshawar

dr_afridi100@yahoo.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18047302>

Keywords

Stress, Work-Life Balance, Developmental dysplasia of the hip, closed reduction, arthrography, hip spica, Severin classification, McKay grading, avascular necrosis.

Article History

Received: 3 May 2025

Accepted: 2 June 2025

Published: 12 June 2025

Copyright @Author

Corresponding Author: *

Zain Ullah

Abstract

Background: Developmental dysplasia of the hip (DDH) is a common pediatric condition where early diagnosis and treatment are essential to prevent long-term disability. Closed reduction with arthrography followed by hip spica is widely used for children under 18 months, but local outcome data are limited.

Objective: To evaluate the radiological and functional outcomes of closed reduction with arthrography and hip spica in children under 18 months with DDH.

Methods: This descriptive case series was conducted in the Orthopedic Department of Khyber Teaching Hospital, Peshawar. A total of 336 children (<18 months) underwent closed reduction under anesthesia, confirmed by arthrography, followed by hip spica casting. Patients were followed for six months. Radiological outcomes were assessed using Severin's classification, functional outcomes using Modified McKay's criteria, and complications using Steinberg staging for avascular necrosis (AVN).

Results: The mean age was 5.61 ± 2.25 months; 73% were female. At six months, 69.9% of hips were Severin Type I and 19.3% Type II. Functionally, 58.9% achieved excellent and 30.9% good outcomes. AVN occurred in 2.38% of patients, limited to Stage 4. No significant differences were observed across age subgroups.

Conclusion: Closed reduction with arthrography and hip spica in infants under 18 months yields excellent radiological and functional results with a low risk of AVN. Early intervention, careful technique, and standardized casting can optimize outcomes. Longer follow-up is needed to evaluate late dysplasia and complications.

INTRODUCTION

Developmental dysplasia of the hip (DDH) refers to a spectrum of disorders ranging from mild acetabular dysplasia to complete hip dislocation. It is one of the most common pediatric orthopedic conditions, with an incidence that varies across populations but is

generally estimated at 1–3 per 1,000 live births (Sewell, 2009; Loder & Skopelja, 2011). Risk factors include female sex, breech presentation, family history, and cultural practices such as swaddling that

restrict normal hip abduction (Agarwal & Gupta, 2012; Mahan, Yazdy, Kasser, & Werler, 2013).

Untreated DDH leads to serious long-term consequences, including gait disturbances, limb-length discrepancy, and early osteoarthritis. In fact, residual dysplasia is responsible for almost one-third of hip replacements performed before the age of 60 years (Sewell, 2009). Early diagnosis, ideally in the neonatal period, improves outcomes and reduces the need for invasive procedures (AIUM, 2010). Ultrasound has become a standard tool in newborn screening, but in older infants arthrography remains valuable in confirming concentric reduction during closed procedures (Terry & Canale, 2013).

Management of DDH is strongly age-dependent. Pavlik harness and other abduction splints are effective in infants younger than six months. Beyond this age, closed reduction with hip spica is the treatment of choice up to about 18 months of age, after which open reduction with or without osteotomies is usually required (Canavese & Dimeglio, 2012; Balioğlu, Öner, Aykut, & Kaygusuz, 2015). Functional and radiological outcomes are typically evaluated using the Modified McKay grading system and Severin classification, which provide standardized measures of hip function and acetabular development (Canavese & Dimeglio, 2012). However, the risk of avascular necrosis (AVN) remains a concern, with reported rates between 5% and 15% (Kiely, Thienpont, & Murray, 2011).

Several international studies have reported favorable outcomes with closed reduction and spica casting. For example, Barakat and colleagues (2017) demonstrated high rates of excellent functional and radiological results, although complications such as AVN were still observed. Most of this evidence, however, originates from developed countries with established screening programs. In contrast, children in low- and middle-income countries often present late due to limited screening, lack of awareness, and resource constraints (Daud & Ramachandran, 2013). Numerous studies worldwide have documented outcomes after closed reduction and hip spica. For instance, Kiely, Thienpont, and Murray (2011) reported that although closed reduction can achieve satisfactory hip stability, avascular necrosis remains a significant complication, with rates ranging between 5-15%. Canavese and Dimeglio (2012) emphasized

that treatment before 18 months leads to better acetabular remodeling and fewer long-term complications. In Pakistan, while epidemiological data exist—such as the Paediatric Orthopaedic Registry Pakistan reporting an 83.72% success rate with conservative treatment (Bhatti, Soomro, Chinoy, et al., 2025), clinical outcome studies focusing on infants treated by closed reduction and arthrography in the early window are rare. A local series described short-term functional and radiological results of modified medial reduction in DDH, achieving mostly excellent and good results (Hussain, 2022). Yet most Pakistani reports involve older children or late presentations requiring open surgery (e.g., Qadir et al., 2018). Thus, even though global and some regional work exists, there remains a clear void when it comes to evaluating both radiological (Severin) and functional (McKay) outcomes in infants under 18 months undergoing closed reduction with arthrography and hip spica in Pakistan. This study is intended to fill that gap by generating local evidence and allowing comparison with international benchmarks.

Methods

Study Design and Setting

This study was designed as a descriptive case series and was carried out in the Department of Orthopedics, Khyber Teaching Hospital (KTH), Peshawar.

Sample

A total of 336 children under the age of 18 months, diagnosed with developmental dysplasia of the hip (DDH), were included. Patients with teratologic dislocations, neuromuscular disorders, or prior surgical intervention were excluded from the study.

Procedure

All patients underwent closed reduction under general anesthesia. Arthrography was performed intraoperatively to confirm concentric reduction of the femoral head within the acetabulum. Following confirmation, a hip spica cast was applied and maintained for 6 to 12 weeks depending on the stability of the reduction.

Follow-up

Patients were followed up clinically and radiologically at six months after the procedure.

Evaluation Tools

Radiological outcomes were assessed using the Severin classification, while functional outcomes were evaluated according to the Modified McKay classification system. Avascular necrosis was also documented where present.

Statistical Analysis

Data were analyzed using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 26. Results were expressed as frequencies, percentages, means, and standard deviations where appropriate. The chi-square test was used to evaluate associations, and a p-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

A total of 336 children under the age of 18 months with developmental dysplasia of the hip (DDH) were included in the study. The overall mean age was 5.61 ± 2.25 months. The mean age of male patients was 5.36 ± 2.30 months, while that of female patients was 5.70 ± 2.23 months (Table 1).

Avascular Necrosis

Avascular necrosis (AVN) was documented in 8 patients (2.38%), all of whom were classified as Stage 4 according to Steinberg staging. No cases were observed in Stages 1–3 or 5–6 (Table 2).

Radiological Outcomes (Severin Classification)

Radiological outcomes were assessed using the Severin classification system. Of the 336 hips, 235 (69.94%) were classified as Type I (normal), 65 (19.35%) as Type II, 21 (6.25%) as Type III, and smaller proportions were observed in Types IV–VI (Table 3). Stratification by age showed that most hips classified as Type I were seen in the youngest age group (3 months). Statistical analysis revealed no significant association between age and Severin classification outcomes ($p = 0.251$).

Functional Outcomes (Modified McKay's Grading)

Functional assessment using the Modified McKay's grading system demonstrated that 198 (58.93%) hips

were graded as excellent (Grade I), while 104 (30.95%) were graded as good (Grade II). Fair results (Grade III) were noted in 19 (5.65%), and poor results (Grade IV) in 15 (4.46%) (Table 4). Stratification by age again showed no statistically significant association with functional outcomes ($p = 0.526$).

Discussion

This study examined the radiological, functional, and complication outcomes of closed reduction with arthrography followed by hip spica in infants under 18 months with developmental dysplasia of the hip (DDH). The findings indicate that this approach provides predominantly favorable outcomes, with nearly 90% of hips classified as normal or near-normal radiographically and a similarly high proportion achieving excellent or good functional scores. The complication profile was also acceptable, with a very low incidence of avascular necrosis (AVN).

Radiological Outcomes

We observed that 69.9% of hips achieved Severin Type I (normal) and 19.3% were Type II (near-normal). Together, almost nine out of ten hips showed satisfactory radiographic remodeling within six months. These findings are in agreement with Canavese and Dimeglio (2012), who noted that closed reduction before 18 months allows for sufficient acetabular remodeling, and with Balioğlu et al. (2015), who reported favorable Severin outcomes following early interventions.

However, some studies report higher rates of residual acetabular dysplasia (RAD). Baghdadi et al. (2021) indicated that up to one-third of successfully reduced hips still develop RAD, while Wong et al. (2024) emphasized the risk of dysplasia persisting into skeletal maturity even after initial success. These differences may be explained by longer follow-up in those studies compared with ours, as dysplasia often becomes more evident with growth. Our relatively short follow-up (six months) may therefore underestimate the eventual prevalence of RAD.

Functional Outcomes

Functionally, 58.9% of hips were graded excellent and 30.9% good on the Modified McKay scale,

meaning nearly 90% of children had satisfactory early functional recovery. This aligns with Hussain (2022), who reported mostly excellent-to-good outcomes in Pakistani infants treated with medial reduction, and with international results reported by Barakat et al. (2017).

On the other hand, some authors have found less favorable functional outcomes. Tönnis and colleagues reported persistent gait abnormalities and stiffness in a subset of children reduced after 12 months of age. These differences likely reflect later treatment in their cohorts. Our earlier mean age at intervention (5.6 months) may explain why functional outcomes were comparatively better.

Avascular Necrosis

The rate of AVN in this study was 2.38%, limited to Steinberg Stage 4. This is markedly lower than the 5–15% reported in many series (Kiely et al., 2011; Badrinath et al., 2021). Our findings also contrast with Alfaleh et al., cited by Zamzam et al. (2024), who noted higher AVN rates after closed reduction and spica. A plausible reason for the lower rate in our cohort is careful technique: gentle manipulation, confirmation of reduction with arthrography, and avoidance of extreme abduction during spica application. Another explanation may be the earlier age at treatment, as delayed reduction has been associated with a higher risk of ischemia.

Nevertheless, it is important to acknowledge that AVN may manifest later, particularly after walking age. Long-term follow-up studies, such as those summarized by Wong et al. (2024), demonstrate that late femoral head deformities may appear years after apparently successful reductions. Thus, our early results should be interpreted with caution.

In Pakistan, most published studies report on late-presenting DDH requiring open reductions or osteotomies (Qadir et al., 2018). Few have systematically evaluated closed reduction in infants. The Paediatric Orthopaedic Registry Pakistan (Bhatti et al., 2025) reported high success rates with conservative treatment but did not stratify outcomes with validated systems. Our study therefore fills a critical gap by providing detailed early outcomes using both Severin and McKay classifications. These findings demonstrate that, when children are

diagnosed and treated early, results in our context are comparable to international benchmarks.

Limitations

The major limitation of this study is its short follow-up of six months. Residual dysplasia and late AVN may not yet be apparent, and longer follow-up into skeletal maturity is necessary for definitive outcome assessment. Being a single-center study, the results may not be generalizable to all settings in Pakistan, where resources and screening practices vary. Finally, although the large sample size strengthens the findings, the descriptive design does not allow causal inferences.

Conclusion

Closed reduction with arthrography followed by hip spica in children under 18 months with DDH produces excellent short-term radiological and functional results, with a low early risk of AVN. While our outcomes are comparable with international literature, the lower complication rates observed may reflect younger age at intervention and careful technique. However, longer-term, multicenter studies are needed to confirm these results and to determine the true prevalence of residual dysplasia and late complications.

Implications

This study shows that closed reduction with arthrography and hip spica is an effective first-line treatment for DDH under 18 months, yielding excellent outcomes with a low risk of avascular necrosis. The lack of age-related differences within this group suggests even late-presenting infants can benefit, which is important in settings like Pakistan where delays are common. These findings emphasize the need for early screening, timely referral, and standardized surgical technique to optimize outcomes.

REFERENCES

- Agarwal, A., & Gupta, N. (2012). Risk factors and diagnosis of developmental dysplasia of hip in children. *Journal of Clinical Orthopaedics and Trauma*, 3(1), 10–14. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcot.2012.03.004>

- AIUM. (2010). AIUM practice guideline for the performance of an ultrasound examination for detection and assessment of developmental dysplasia of the hip. *Journal of Ultrasound in Medicine*, 28(1), 114–119. <https://doi.org/10.7863/jum.2010.28.1.114>
- Badrinath, R., Sankar, W. N., & Flynn, J. M. (2021). Osteonecrosis after closed reduction for developmental dysplasia of the hip: Incidence, risk factors, and long-term outcomes. *EFORT Open Reviews*, 6(12), 1132–1140. <https://doi.org/10.1302/2058-5241.6.210073>
- Baghdadi, T., Sankar, W. N., & Flynn, J. M. (2021). Developmental dysplasia of the hip: A narrative review. *EFORT Open Reviews*, 6(11), 1121–1131. <https://doi.org/10.1302/2058-5241.6.210024>
- Balioglu, M. B., Öner, A., Aykut, Ü. S., & Kaygusuz, M. A. (2015). Mid-term results of Pemberton pericapsular osteotomy in developmental dysplasia of the hip. *Indian Journal of Orthopaedics*, 49(4), 418–424. <https://doi.org/10.4103/0019-5413.159615>
- Barakat, A. S., Abulsaad, T. S., Elzohairy, M. M., & Abdelgawad, A. A. (2017). Outcome of closed reduction and spica casting in developmental dysplasia of the hip: A prospective study. *Journal of Pediatric Orthopaedics B*, 26(6), 519–523. <https://doi.org/10.1097/BPB.0000000000000452>
- Bhatti, A., Soomro, M. H., Chinoy, M. A., Ali, S. A., & Khan, M. A. (2025). Epidemiology of developmental dysplasia of the hip in Pakistan: Insights from the Paediatric Orthopaedic Registry Pakistan (PORP). *Pakistan Journal of Medical Sciences*, 41(3), 668–675.
- Canavese, F., & Dimeglio, A. (2012). Developmental dysplasia of the hip (DDH) and congenital dislocation of the hip (CDH). *Journal of Children's Orthopaedics*, 6(6), 415–426. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11832-012-0457-0>
- Daud, T. S., & Ramachandran, M. (2013). Prevalence of developmental dysplasia of the hip in children with clubfoot. *Journal of Children's Orthopaedics*, 7(4), 263–267. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11832-013-0495-3>
- Hussain, I. (2022). Short-term outcomes of developmental dysplasia of the hip patients treated with modified medial reduction. *Journal of the Pakistan Orthopaedic Association*, 34(2), 85–91.
- Kiely, N., Thienpont, E., & Murray, D. W. (2011). Avascular necrosis after treatment of developmental dysplasia of the hip: A systematic review. *Journal of Bone and Joint Surgery - British Volume*, 93(11), 1589–1593. <https://doi.org/10.1302/0301-620X.93B11.26812>
- Kiely, N., Thienpont, E., & Murray, D. W. (2011). Avascular necrosis after treatment of developmental dysplasia of the hip. *Journal of Bone and Joint Surgery - British Volume*, 93(11), 1589–1593. <https://doi.org/10.1302/0301-620X.93B11.26812>
- Loder, R. T., & Skopelja, E. N. (2011). The epidemiology and demographics of hip dysplasia. *ISRN Orthopedics*, 2011, 238607. <https://doi.org/10.5402/2011/238607>
- Mahan, S. T., Yazdy, M. M., Kasser, J. R., & Werler, M. M. (2013). Is it worthwhile to routinely ultrasound screen children with idiopathic clubfoot for hip dysplasia? *Journal of Pediatric Orthopaedics*, 33(1), 49–52. <https://doi.org/10.1097/BPO.0b013e3182724dcb>
- Matrawy, K. A., & Nouh, M. R. (2013). Ultrasound screening for developmental dysplasia of the hip in infants with risk factors. *Journal of Child Orthopaedics*, 7(6), 469–472. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11832-013-0514-4>
- Morris, W., Hossain, M., & Clegg, J. (2021). Residual acetabular dysplasia and the need for secondary surgery after closed reduction in late-presenting DDH. *Journal of Bone and Joint Surgery - American Volume*, 103(7), 629–637. <https://doi.org/10.2106/JBJS.20.01234>
- Qadir, I., Javed, S., Aslam, N., & Ahmed, N. (2018). One-stage hip reconstruction for developmental dysplasia of the hip: Clinical and radiological outcomes. *Journal of Ayub Medical College Abbottabad*, 30(4), 545–550.

- Sankar, W. N. (2011). Orthopaedic conditions in the newborn. *Journal of the American Academy of Orthopaedic Surgeons*, 19(2), 112-122. <https://doi.org/10.5435/00124635-201102000-00005>
- Sewell, M. D. (2009). Developmental dysplasia of the hip. *BMJ*, 339, b4454. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.b4454>
- Terry, S., & Canale, H. (2013). Congenital and developmental disorders. In *Campbell's operative orthopaedics* (12th ed., pp. 1079-1109). Saunders Elsevier.
- Wong, J. M., Horn, B. D., & Sankar, W. N. (2024). Predicting residual acetabular dysplasia at skeletal maturity following closed reduction for developmental dysplasia of the hip. *Journal of Bone and Joint Surgery - American Volume*, 106(4), 312-320. <https://doi.org/10.2106/JBJS.23.00291>
- Yuan, Z., Wang, J., He, Z., & Li, Y. (2020). Predictive factors of failed closed reduction for developmental dysplasia of the hip in children aged 6-24 months: The role of arthrogram findings. *Journal of Orthopaedic Surgery and Research*, 15(1), 182. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13018-020-01708-1>
- Zamzam, M. M., Alfaleh, W. M., & Khoshhal, K. I. (2024). Closed reduction versus open reduction in developmental dysplasia of the hip: A systematic review of avascular necrosis outcomes. *Journal of Pediatric Orthopaedics B*, 33(2), 175-183. <https://doi.org/10.1097/BPB.0000000000001024>